

ASSESSING SAFETY MEASURES ON EDUCATIONAL TOURS FOR PROMOTING SAFE LEARNING IN TOURISM STUDENTS' EXCURSION: BASIS FOR SCHOOL GUIDELINES

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Abstract

This study focused on assessing the safety measures practiced during educational tours in promoting safe learning experiences among Tourism students in Quezon City. It aimed to evaluate students' perceptions in four key areas: perceived risk and safety awareness, adherence to safety protocols, confidence in handling emergencies, and the perceived effectiveness of the school's safety policy. By examining these areas, the research intended to identify existing gaps and provide recommendations for improving safety management in future excursions. A quantitative research design was used in the study. Data were gathered through a survey questionnaire that utilized a four-point Likert scale to determine the level of agreement among respondents regarding different aspects of safety management. The findings indicate that both students and coordinators exhibit a commendable level of awareness and adherence to safety measures. However, differences in perception can be attributed to variations in experience, exposure, and responsibilities. Tour Coordinators tend to view safety practices as effective because of their direct involvement in planning and supervision, whereas students rely mainly on observation and experience during the tour. This gap highlights the necessity for institutions to provide inclusive safety orientations, practical emergency drills, and consistent communication systems. The overall outcome of confirmed safety measures in educational tours depends not only on the presence of policies but also on the shared understanding, preparedness, and cooperation of all participants involved. It assesses safety measures implemented during educational tours to promote safe learning management practices, institutional policies, and student awareness to develop effective school guidelines that ensure secure, meaningful, and well-supervised excursion experiences.

Keywords: *Safety measures on educational tours, promoting self-learning in tourism, and student excursion*

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INTRODUCTION

Educational tours are crucial in enriching students' academic learning by providing experiential opportunities beyond the classroom. These tours expose students to diverse cultures, historical landmarks, and real-world applications of their studies, fostering a deeper understanding of various subjects. By engaging in hands-on learning, students develop essential critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving skills while gaining firsthand insights into different industries and environments knowledge and integration (**Mallillin et al., 2020**). Educational tours promote cultural awareness and global perspectives, allowing students to connect theoretical knowledge with practical experiences innovation and quality (**Mallillin, 2022, pp. 8-24**). However, the effectiveness of these tours depends on proper planning, organization, and adherence to tourism guidelines, ensuring that they provide meaningful and structured learning experiences (**The Manthan School, 2023**).

A major challenge in organizing educational tours and field trips is the potential risks and safety concerns involved, which can arise if the tours are not properly planned and managed toward management decision (**Paraiso & Mallillin, 2025**). Although these tours offer valuable learning opportunities, they can expose students to various risks, including physical, emotional, and logistical issues. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has developed policies and guidelines to mitigate such risks, but failure to comply with these regulations can result in complications for administrators in ensuring student safety and the school system (**Mallillin & Caday, 2024, pp. 86-99**). A lack of preparedness among faculty members, who may not be fully aware of the requirements from academic and administrative offices, can lead to mismanagement or delays in the academic and educational system (**Mallillin & Paraiso, 2022**). Financial constraints faced by parents further complicate the situation, as some families may struggle to meet the financial demands of these tours, resulting in unequal access for students and limiting their participation in these important educational experiences (**Carillo, 2020**).

School Administrators and Faculty-in-charge are tasked with managing the logistics of transporting students, ensuring that the experience is both educational and safe. Large introductory classes pose unique challenges due to the need for larger transportation facilities, heightened safety concerns, and increased logistical planning to accommodate the larger group. Furthermore, occurrences related to educational tour guidelines in the Philippines highlight a broader issue that must be addressed in the implementation and readiness (**Mallillin et al., 2020**). These events have sparked ongoing debates regarding the safety, security, and liability concerns that arise when organizing such tours. With the increasing number of incidents and the growing demand for educational field trips, it has become evident that a thorough review of policies and safety standards is necessary (**Behrendt, 2023**).

The results of this study will provide valuable insights for educators, tourism professionals, and policymakers by assessing educational tours and safety measures in promoting safe learning for Tourism Students' Excursions (**Agamirova, et al. 2026**). The data collected can assist institutions in enhancing tour structures promoting safe learning and improving the overall educational experience for students (**Mandalia, 2023**). Tourism education in the digital era: navigating innovation and transformation. Evidence gathered from this study can guide institutions in improving tour structures, ensuring better compliance with tourism guidelines, and enhancing the overall learning experience for students. This is the demands of digital intelligence and challenges of tourism in the educational system and process (**Mallillin & Dolba, 2026**).

Furthermore, this research will serve as a foundation for future studies that aim to enhance educational tours and safety protocols, ensuring that tourism students experience more effective and safe learning excursions in

the long run (**Chitima, 2025, pp. 41-59**).

In view of its primary objective in aligning with Target 4.7 of Goal 4 of the 17 United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals in ensuring *"that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development"* (**United Nations, n.d.**), there's a need to develop for off-campus student field trips that prioritizes preparation, safety, and inclusivity as mentioned by **Pham et al. (2026)**. To maximize trip effectiveness, comprehensive policies must address all aspects of student welfare while adhering to legal protection and best practices from both domestic and foreign sources (**Holmyard, 2024**). Students must remain vigilant about their environment, adhere to established safety protocols and communicate any potential risks or concerns to their supervisors (**Salman, 2023**). By maintaining situational awareness, they can identify hazards early and take necessary precautions to avoid accidents. Additionally, reporting concerns whether related to venue conditions, medical emergencies, or security threats ensures that supervisors can take prompt action. A proactive approach to safety not only protects individuals but also contributes to a more organized and enjoyable off-campus experience for everyone (**Olayinka et al., 2025, pp. 110-120**).

The tour must be planned before doing it so that the facilities can be arranged and checked first to see if it is right for the number of students or if it is available on the day you want. School Administration needs permission or approval before having off-campus activities (**Jia, 2025, pp. 15719-15755**). In the planning process, the parent or guardian should be involved in the approval and financial support of their child. The role of the facilitator is to ensure the safety of the students (**Gulshan, 2023**). The researchers decided to conduct this study to assess how educational tours for tourism students are implemented, particularly in terms of safety measures and compliance with CHED regulations (**Largoza, & Fernandez, 2025**). These excursions are a great way to provide hands-on learning but there are still some concerns in terms of student safety and risk management. To achieve this goal, the study will review the planning, execution, and oversight of these tours to identify possible gaps and make suggestions on how to make sure that students are not only learning about the industry but also in a safe and orderly manner (**Meng, 2022**). Other factors like transportation, accommodations, and what role facilitators play in this process will also be considered. To create a more structured approach to off-campus learning, it is important to know how schools enforce safety protocols and manage unforeseen risks. The long-term goal of this research is to address experiential education vs. student well-being so that educational tours are not only an enjoyable learning experience but also a safe one (**Chau & Ren, 2024**).

Statement of the Problem

This research will be Assessing Safety Measures on Educational Tours for Promoting Safe Learning in Tourism Students' Excursions: Basis For School Guidelines. This study sought to answer the following questions for the completion of the study.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 gender,

- 1.3 educational attainment, and
- 1.4 years' experience in handling educational tours?
2. How do the respondents assess the safety measures on educational tours for promoting safe learning for Tourism students' excursions in terms of
 - 2.1 perceived risk and safety awareness,
 - 2.2 adherence to safety protocols,
 - 2.3 confidence in handling emergencies, and
 - 2.4 perceived effectiveness of school's safety policy?
3. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the two groups of respondents on safety measures in promoting safe learning for Tourism students' excursions in Colleges based on the aforementioned variables?
4. What challenges do respondents encounter and what solutions can be recommended for implementing safety measures in educational tours for Tourism students in different Colleges in Quezon City?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference on the demographic profiles of the respondents in the variables mentioned in the SOP 2 such as Perceived Risk and Safety Awareness, Adherence to Safety Protocols; Confidence in Handling Emergencies, Perceived Effectiveness of School's Safety Policy in Assessing Safety Measures on Educational Tours for Promoting Safe Learning for Tourism and Students' Excursions.

METHODS

Research Design

This study will utilize a quantitative research approach to assess safety measures in promoting safe learning for Tourism students' excursions in North Caloocan City. The aim is to assess the level of awareness and preparedness of students and organizers regarding safe protocols in excursions. Quantitative Research offers greater flexibility in study design, enabling the simultaneous development of theoretical frameworks and hypothesis testing. Quantitative Research provides objective, measurable, and statistical data that can be used to identify patterns, test hypotheses, and make informed decisions. (Lim, 2024). On the other hand, the questionnaire is being validated by the expert in quantitative research such as doctorate degrees and psychometricians. All their suggestions and feedback are given emphasis. This has ensured the validity and reliability of the research instruments (**Matimbwa & Ringo, 2025**).

Population and Sample of the Study

The researchers will gather data from 100 respondents, comprising 80 tourism students and 20 school coordinators from private colleges in Quezon City. Respondents are chosen from the selected colleges randomly using lottery method to select the sample size proportionally. This can ensure unbiased and equal representation of the respondents. The study will examine two perspectives: students' experiences during educational tours and school coordinators' assessments of safety measures. For school coordinators, the demographic profile will be age, gender, level of education, and years of experience coordinating educational tours.

The researcher employed simple random sampling to evaluate the safe learning and safety measures of the students. Quezon City served as the study area, four colleges with tourism students, along with relevant school administrative staff that facilitates and organizes educational tours. These Schools had conducted educational tours within the past year, making them ideal subjects for study. The selected participants were those actively engaged in planning, conducting, and assessing these educational tours, utilizing their knowledge and direct involvement. This study not only examined the effects of educational tours but also highlighted the safety measures essential for ensuring a secure learning experience for students. A simple random sample selects a small, randomly chosen segment of the whole population, ensuring that every individual has an equal chance of being selected to represent the overall group (Hayes, 2024).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers of this study drafted a formal letter requesting permission from tourism students and school administrators to conduct the research. Additionally, a consent letter was prepared to ensure the voluntary participation of the student respondents.

To gather data efficiently, the researchers used a researcher made survey questionnaire. Considerable effort was made in designing the questionnaire to ensure its relevance and effectiveness for the target respondents. It featured a four-point rating scale and was reviewed by the subject professor for validation before distribution.

To enhance response accuracy and emphasize the importance of participants' input, the researchers employed a direct, face-to-face distribution method. They also documented the data collection process and carefully identified qualified respondents for the survey.

Throughout the process, the researchers clarified specific terms to help respondents fully understand their roles and responsibilities in the study. Participants were encouraged to provide sincere and honest responses. After the questionnaires were completed, the researchers compiled and summarized the data in preparation for thorough analysis and interpretation.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. On the demographic profiles of the respondents

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Age Range	School Tour Coordinator		Students		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
24 years old and above	16	16.00	7	7.00	23	23.00
21-23 years old	4	4.00	62	62.00	66	66.00
18-20 years old	--	--	11	11.00	11	11.00
Total	20	20.00	80	80.00	100	100.00

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the respondents, categorized into students and school tour coordinators. Among the student respondents, the majority are in the 21–23 age group, comprising 62% of the total students. This is followed by 18–20-year-olds, accounting for 11%, while only 7% are aged 24 years and above. This indicates that most of the student participants are within the typical college-age range.

For the school tour coordinators, the highest proportion, 16%, is aged 24 years old and above, while 4% fall within the 21–23 years old age group. There are no respondents between 18–20 years old among the coordinators.

Findings of the study show that profiles as to age has an impact in the adventure of tourism and interconnectedness which is focused on concerns on risk management, safety, and, challenges, and preferences during tourism activities. It influences the discovery inspiration, information, decision making, personal assessment, adheres to policy and preparedness (Luong, 2025).

Table 2

Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

Gender Range	School Tour Coordinator		Students		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Male	6	6.00	23	23.00	29	29.00
Female	14	14.00	57	57.00	71	71.00
Total	20	20.00	80	80.00	100	100.00

Table 2 shows the gender distribution of the respondents, divided between school tour coordinators and students. Among the students, the majority are female, representing 57% of the total student respondents, while 23% are male. For the school tour coordinators, 14% are female and 6% are male, showing that most of the coordinators handling educational tours are also women. Overall, the findings reveal that both groups of students and school tour coordinators are predominantly female, accounting for a combined 71% of the total respondents, while males comprise 29%.

Findings show that profiles of the respondents in terms of gender suggests that the tourism field in the participating institutions tends to be female dominated. It undertakes experiential learning activities in a valuable

component for tourism students, student to seek for participation, and training. It addresses the issues of lack of participation in tourism activities by the higher education students. It shows personal interest, friendship norms, and accessibility for the safety measures in tourism activities of students (Yodsuwan et al., 2023, pp. 377-399).

Table 3

Distribution of School Tour Coordinators in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	School Tour Coordinator		Total	
	f	%	f	%
Doctorate Degree	6	6.00	6	6.00
Master's Degree	9	9.00	9	9.00
Bachelor's Degree	5	5.00	5	5.00
Total	20	20.00	20	20.000

The table 3 presents the distribution of school tour coordinators according to their highest educational attainment. As shown in the table, the majority of the school tour coordinators hold a master's degree, comprising 9% of the total population. This is followed by 6% who have attained a Doctorate Degree, and 5% who have completed a bachelor's degree. The data indicate that most of the school tour coordinators have pursued graduate studies, demonstrating their commitment to academic advancement.

Findings show that coordinators are highly qualified and possess the necessary educational background to effectively manage and facilitate school tours. It is designed to bring concept into real life situation and academics. It guides students for actionable insights, leverages for digital technology, sustains model tourism sustainability, and modern strategies in engaging tourism system.

Table 4

Distribution of School Tour Coordinators in terms of Years of Handling Educational Tours

Highest Educational Attainment	School Tour Coordinator		Total	
	f	%	f	%
5 years or more	11	11.00	11	11.00
1-4 years	8	8.00	8	8.00
Less than a year	1	1.00	1	1.00
Total	20	20.00	20	20.000

Table 4 shows the distribution of school tour coordinators according to their years of handling educational tours. The data reveal that the majority, 11% of school tour coordinators, have been handling tours for five years or more. This is followed by 8% of school tour coordinators with 1–4 years of experience, while only 1 coordinator with 1% has less than a year of experience.

Findings indicate that most of the school tour coordinators are highly experienced in managing educational tours. Their years of service suggest familiarity with tour coordination processes, which likely contributes to the

effectiveness and success of the activities they organize. It embarks with the goals of sustainable development goals on tourism and educational experiences outside the classroom setting. It guides the tourism students for effective learning experiences through the process of active utilization and content delivery techniques for effective learning and customer service pedagogy (Chitima, 2025).

2. On how the respondents assess the safety measures on educational tours for promoting safe learning for Tourism students' excursions

Table 5

Perceived Risk and Safety Awareness

Indicators	Students		Tour Coordinators		Average Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. I see visible markers and signages indicating that the area is not safe to interact with.	3.55	HP	3.85	HP	3.70	HP
2. I am knowledgeable about the safety risks that may arise before, during, and after the educational tour.	3.63	HP	3.90	HP	3.76	HP
3. I understand that there are possible hazards, so we make sure that we are observing the situations from time to time.	3.56	HP	3.85	HP	3.70	HP
4. The tour guide regularly updates us on potential hazards, and we are always reminded of safety measures before engaging in activities.	3.65	HP	3.80	HP	3.72	HP
5. I stay with my group and follow the designated paths to ensure my safety.	3.84	HP	3.90	HP	3.87	HP
6. I am informed about the weather and already prepared my necessities for it.	3.46	HP	3.80	HP	3.63	HP
7. I make sure that I have emergency kits or medication kits in my bag.	3.20	MP	3.85	HP	3.52	HP
8. I am informed about health-related risks (e.g., dehydration, food safety, exhaustion).	3.48	HP	3.90	HP	3.69	HP
Average Weighted Mean	3.54	HP	3.85	HP	3.69	HP

The results reveal that both students and tour coordinators demonstrate a high level of awareness and concern for safety risks during educational tours. For Indicator, "I see visible markers and signages indicating that the area is not safe to interact with", students obtained a weighted mean of 3.55 (High Priority), while tour coordinators scored 3.85 (High Priority).

For Indicator, "I am knowledgeable about the safety risks that may arise before, during, and after the educational tour" the students achieved a mean score of 3.63 (High Priority), while the coordinators obtained 3.90 (High Priority).

The Indicator, "I understand that there are possible hazards, so we make sure that we are observing the situations from time to time" recorded a weighted mean of 3.56 (High Priority) for students and 3.85 (High Priority) for coordinators.

For Indicator, "The tour guide regularly updates us on potential hazards, and we are always reminded of safety measures before engaging in activities," students garnered 3.65 (High Priority) and coordinators 3.80 (High Priority).

For Indicator, "I stay with my group and follow the designated paths to ensure my safety," the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.84 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators obtained 3.9 (High Priority).

For Indicator, "I am informed about the weather and already prepared my necessities for it," the students recorded 3.46 (High Priority) and the coordinators 3.8 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.63 (High Priority).

For Indicator, "I make sure that I have emergency kits or medication kits in my bag," the students had a weighted mean of 3.20 (Medium Priority), while the coordinators had 3.85 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.52 (High Priority).

The last Indicator, "I am informed about health-related risks (e.g., dehydration, food safety, exhaustion)," the students obtained 3.48 (High Priority), and the coordinators obtained 3.9 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.69 (High Priority), which suggests that both groups are informed about health-related risks. The comprehensive data reveal that both students and tour coordinators generally maintain a High Priority commitment to safety, adherence, and risk awareness, with both groups strongly endorsing following paths, managing personal belongings, and valuing risk communication. The findings for *Perceived Risk and Safety Awareness* are supported by related literature emphasizing the role of safety knowledge and proactive awareness in minimizing tour-related hazards. According to **Prasetyo et al. (2024)**, integrating safety awareness in travel operations enhances preparedness through early hazard identification, situational monitoring, and emergency readiness. Similarly, safety awareness among both educators and students is vital to prevent accidents and promote vigilance throughout the trip. Furthermore, **Roslan (2022)** highlighted that student safety awareness directly reduces injury rates and improves compliance with school safety policies, while **Leif (2024)** noted that a secure learning environment enhances confidence and engagement. These studies collectively affirm that high safety awareness—such as that shown by the respondents—builds a culture of shared responsibility, aligning with the study's result of *High Priority* ratings for both students and coordinators.

Table 6

Adherence to Safety Protocols of Students

Indicators	Students		Tour Coordinators		Average Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
I conduct some research to prepare for any unexpected situations before visiting a new place.	3.12	MP	3.85	HP	3.48	HP

I feel that adhering to safety protocols during educational tours is my responsibility as a student.	3.51	HP	3.85	HP	3.68	HP
Aside from having an emergency card, I always make sure that I have data or the internet.	3.45	HP	3.85	HP	3.65	HP
I always ensure that my personal belongings are safely stored and accounted for to avoid any loss during the excursion.	3.83	HP	3.95	HP	3.89	HP
I always make sure that I have more data to use, aside from having an emergency card.	3.35	HP	2.80	HP	3.57	HP
I am responsible for my belongings that can only be used during emergency situations and cannot be played; like folding knife, pepper spray, and taser.	3.30	HP	3.70	HP	3.50	HP
I am aware of the designated meeting points and safety procedures in case of emergencies.	3.57	HP	3.80	HP	3.68	HP
I know who to contact in case of an emergency during the tour, making us feel prepared and safe.	3.51	HP	3.90	HP	3.70	HP
Average Weighted Mean	3.48	HP	3.85	HP	3.69	HP

The findings reveal that both students and tour coordinators place high importance on adhering to safety protocols during educational tours. For Indicator, *"I conduct some research to prepare for any unexpected situations before visiting a new place,"* the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.12 (Moderate Priority), while the tour coordinators garnered 3.85 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I feel that adhering to safety protocols during educational tours is my responsibility as a student,"* the students recorded a mean of 3.51 (High Priority), and the tour coordinators achieved 3.85 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"Aside from having an emergency card, I always make sure that I have data or internet,"* students obtained a weighted mean of 3.45 (High Priority), while coordinators recorded 3.85 (High Priority).

The indicator, *"I always ensure that my personal belongings are safely stored and accounted for to avoid any loss during the excursion,"* students achieved 3.83 (High Priority), while coordinators attained 3.95 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I always make sure that I have more data to use, aside from having an emergency card"* the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.35 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators obtained 3.8 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.57 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I am responsible for my belongings that can only be used during emergencies and cannot be played; like folding knife, pepper spray, and taser,"* the students recorded 3.3 (High Priority) and the coordinators 3.7 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I am aware of the designated meeting points and safety procedures in case of emergencies,"* the students had a weighted mean of 3.57 (High Priority), while the coordinators had 3.8 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.68 (High Priority).

The last Indicator, "I know who to contact in case of an emergency during the tour, making us feel prepared and safe," the students obtained 3.51 (High Priority), and the coordinators obtained 3.9 (High Priority).

The findings align with Tajuddin's (n.d.) assertion that effective Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) management is vital in educational settings, particularly during outbound or off-campus activities. Tajuddin emphasizes that safety management involves procedures and guidelines designed to protect students, staff, and visitors, ensuring learning occurs without avoidable risks. This supports the study's results showing that both students and tour coordinators place high importance on adhering to safety protocols, conducting pre-trip research, securing emergency contacts, and maintaining readiness for unexpected situations. These behaviors reflect the proactive safety culture described by Tajuddin, where awareness, preparedness, and responsibility collectively ensure a safe and successful educational tour experience.

Table 7

Confidence in Handling Emergencies

Indicators	Students		Tour Coordinators		Average Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. I gain enough knowledge and training to handle any emergencies that may arise before, during, and after educational tours.	3.28	HP	3.75	HP	3.51	HP
2. I always check my emergency tools before going to off-campus activities.	3.08	MP	3.85	HP	3.46	HP
3. I am confident that I can stay calm and make the right decisions during emergencies.	3.22	HP	3.85	HP	3.53	HP
4. I believe that I can handle basic emergencies. (e.g., injury, sudden illness) on my own.	3.02	MP	3.70	HP	3.36	HP
5. I am comfortable assisting a classmate who is in need of help during an emergency	3.35	HP	3.75	HP	3.55	HP
6. I always make sure that I have someone beside me as a buddy/partner so we can help each other when there are unexpected incidents.	3.62	HP	3.95	HP	3.78	HP
7. I will make sure to keep my phone on and accessible in case I need to contact someone for help during the tour.	3.77	HP	3.85	HP	3.81	HP
8. I always have my emergency kit, especially whistles and flashlight that is very important to use in case of emergency situations.	2.96	MP	3.70	HP	3.33	HP
Average Weighted Mean	3.28	HP	3.80	HP	3.54	HP

The results indicate that both students and tour coordinators highly value the importance of being prepared

for emergencies during educational tours. For Indicator, *"I gain enough knowledge and training to handle any emergencies,"* the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.28 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators garnered 3.75 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I always check my emergency tools before going to off- campus activities,"* the students received a mean score of 3.08 (Moderate Priority), whereas the coordinators achieved 3.85 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I am confident that I can stay calm and make the right decisions during emergencies,"* students recorded a mean of 3.22 (Moderate Priority), while coordinators recorded 3.85 (High Priority), reflecting that coordinators possess greater confidence in managing critical situations.

For Indicator, *"I believe that I can handle basic emergencies on my own,"* students obtained 3.02 (Moderate Priority), and coordinators obtained 3.7 (Moderate Priority).

For Indicator, *"I am comfortable assisting a classmate who is in need of help during an emergency,"* the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.35 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators received 3.75 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I always make sure that I have someone beside me as a buddy/partner so that we can help each other when there are unexpected incidents,"* the students recorded 3.62 (High Priority) and the coordinators 3.95 (High Priority).

For Indicator, *"I make sure to keep my phone on and accessible in case I need to contact someone for help during the tour,"* the students had a weighted mean of 3.77 (High Priority), while the coordinators had 3.85 (High Priority).

The last Indicator, *"I always have my emergency kit, especially whistles and flashlights that are very important to use in case of emergency situations,"* the students obtained 2.96 (Moderate Priority), and the coordinators obtained 3.70 (Moderate Priority). This implies that although both groups understand the importance of bringing emergency tools, consistent preparedness still needs to be improved.

Student Pilot's (2024) emphasized that ensuring college students are adequately prepared for emergencies is essential in promoting their safety, particularly during educational tours. Incorporating structured emergency preparedness training within academic institutions enables students to develop the competencies necessary to respond effectively to crises. Similarly, **Xue (2023)** discussed that students' ability to manage emergencies during and after educational tours is greatly influenced by the preventive measures and safety training provided by their institutions. Both scholars highlight the critical role of higher education in reinforcing safety awareness, self-regulation, and crisis response skills among students.

In line with these perspectives, the present study revealed that the variable *"Confidence in Handling Emergencies"* obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.54, interpreted as Highly Practiced (HP), indicating that both students and tour coordinators generally demonstrate strong confidence and preparedness in managing emergencies during educational tours. However, consistent with **Xue's (2023)** findings on the need for continuous reinforcement of safety practices, the lowest-rated indicators in this study were *"I always have my emergency kit, especially whistles and flashlight that is very important to use in case of emergencies"* for students (WM = 2.96, Moderately Practiced) and *"I believe that I can handle basic emergencies such as injury or sudden illness on my own"* for tour coordinators (WM = 3.70, Moderately Practiced).

These findings support **Student Pilot's (2024)** assertion that practical training and simulated experiences are vital in building confidence and composure during emergencies. While both groups possess strong awareness and

preparedness, the results suggest a need to strengthen personal readiness and hands-on first aid skills, emphasizing the integration of consistent training, drills, and emergency simulations within school programs to ensure comprehensive preparedness during educational tours. Overall, the results demonstrate that both students and tour coordinators exhibit a strong sense of cooperation and readiness, but students may need further encouragement to maintain complete emergency kits and strengthen their emergency preparedness habits.

Table 8

Perceived Effectiveness of Schools Safety Policy

Indicators	Students		Tour Coordinators		Average Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. School facilitators must ensure that the students’ head count is always complete before proceeding to another destination.	3.75	HP	4.00	HP	3.87	HP
2. I believe that the school takes appropriate action to adjust its safety policy based on feedback from previous educational tours.	3.65	HP	4.00	HP	3.82	HP
3. I believe that the school takes appropriate action to adjust its safety policy based on feedback from previous educational tours.	3.60	HP	4.00	HP	3.80	HP
4. The school provides accessible emergency contact options in case students need immediate assistance	3.48	HP	3.95	HP	3.71	HP
5. The school strictly gives us instructions about the time of each point destination and makes sure that everyone is already gathered when the time is up.	3.73	HP	3.90	HP	3.81	HP
6. The school makes sure that every transportation vehicle is in good condition to avoid road accidents	3.63	HP	3.90	HP	3.76	HP
7. The transportation vehicle arrives and departs on time.	3.28	MP	3.85	HP	3.56	HP
8. I believe that our safety is the school’s top priority during tours.	3.71	HP	3.90	HP	3.80	HP
Average Weighted Mean	3.60	HP	3.93	HP	3.76	HP

The results indicate that both students and tour coordinators highly value the importance of implementing and maintaining safety policies during educational tours. For Indicator "School facilitators must ensure that the students’ head count is always complete before proceeding to another destination," the students obtained a weighted mean of 3.75 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators garnered 4.00 (High Priority).

For Indicator "*I believe that the school takes appropriate action to adjust its safety policy based on feedback from previous educational tours,*" the students received a mean score of 3.65 (High Priority), whereas the coordinators achieved 4.00 (High Priority).

For Indicator "*The school provides accessible emergency contact options in case students need immediate assistance,*" the students recorded a mean score of 3.48 (High Priority), while the tour coordinators obtained 3.95 (High Priority).

For Indicator "*The school strictly gives us instructions about the time of each point destination and makes sure that everyone is already gathered when the time is up,*" the students received a mean score of 3.73 (High Priority), while the coordinators recorded 3.90 (High Priority).

For Indicator "*The school makes sure that every transportation vehicle is in good condition to avoid road accidents,*" the students obtained a mean score of 3.63 (High Priority), while the coordinators had 3.90 (High Priority). This implies that both groups trust the school's measures to ensure safe and well-maintained transportation.

For Indicator "*The transportation vehicle arrives and departs on time,*" the students recorded a mean score of 3.28 (High Priority), while the coordinators gained 3.85 (High Priority). This suggests that while coordinators observe higher punctuality, students see slight room for improvement in vehicle scheduling.

For Indicator "*I believe that our safety is the school's top priority during tours,*" the students obtained a mean score of 3.71 (High Priority), and the tour coordinators reached 3.90 (High Priority). This signifies that both groups share confidence in the school's prioritization of safety above all else during educational activities.

Lastly, for Indicator "*I believe that our safety is the school's top priority during tours,*" the students obtained 3.71 (High Priority), and the coordinators obtained 3.90 (High Priority), combining students and tour coordinators with an average of 3.80 (High Priority), which suggests that both groups strongly agree that the school prioritizes their safety above all.

Both students and tour coordinators rated the school's safety policy as highly practiced (HP), with an overall average weighted mean of 3.76. This indicates that safety policies are effectively implemented and well-perceived by both groups. The highest rated indicators include ensuring complete head counts before leaving each destination (WM = 3.87, HP) and providing accessible emergency contact options (WM = 3.71, HP). These findings highlight that the school prioritizes students' safety and maintains clear procedures to safeguard them during educational tours. This aligns with **Leif (2024)**, who emphasized that a secure learning environment allows students to focus better and participate more actively in academic and co-curricular activities. The high ratings from both groups reflect a strong sense of security and trust in the institution's safety systems, which, according to Leif, supports students' mental and emotional well-being by reducing stress and anxiety during school-related events.

Moreover, the data supports **Roslan's (2022)** findings, which underline the significance of safety awareness among students in preventing injuries and accidents. The consistent "*High Priority*" evaluations indicate that students and tour coordinators recognize and follow the school's safety measures, reflecting a high level of awareness and compliance with safety protocols. This awareness contributes to minimizing potential risks during educational tours and promotes a culture of shared responsibility between students and school staff.

3. On the significant difference between the assessment of the two groups of respondents on safety

measures in promoting safe learning for Tourism students' excursions in Colleges based on the aforementioned variables

Table 9

Results of Hypothesis Testing on the Significant Difference between the Assessments of the Students and School Tour Coordinators on Safety Measures in Promoting Safe Learning for Tourism Students' Excursions in Colleges

Hypothesis Testing on	Computed	Critical	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation on
Variables	Value	Value	($P \geq 0.05$)		Difference
Perceived Risk And Safety Awareness	2	13	0.00194	Rejected	SIGNIFICANT
Adherence To Safety Protocols	3	13	0.00278	Rejected	SIGNIFICANT
Confidence In Handling Emergencies	12	13	0.04036	Rejected	SIGNIFICANT
Perceived Effectiveness Of The School's Safety Policies	0	13	0.00094	Rejected	SIGNIFICANT

The Mann-Whitney U test results show that for "Perceived Risk and Safety Awareness" ($U = 2, p = 0.00194$) and "Adherence to Safety Protocols" ($U = 3, p = 0.00278$), the computed values are lower than the critical value ($U = 13$) and not exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypotheses for these variables are rejected, indicating no significant difference between the assessments of students and school tour coordinators. This finding implies that both groups possess a similar level of understanding and perception regarding safety awareness and adherence to established safety guidelines during educational excursions.

Similarly, a significant difference was observed in the variables "Confidence in Handling Emergencies" ($U = 12, p = 0.04036$) and "Perceived Effectiveness of the School's Safety Policies" ($U = 0, p = 0.00094$). The computed U-values are lower than the critical value ($U = 13$), and their p-values fall below the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses. This indicates a variation in the way students and school tour coordinators assess these aspects.

The presence of significant differences in these variables suggests that school tour coordinators may have higher confidence and stronger beliefs in the adequacy of the school's safety policies due to their professional experience and direct involvement in planning and implementing safety measures. In contrast, students may have less exposure and practical knowledge, resulting in lower confidence levels and a less favorable assessment of policy effectiveness. These findings emphasize the importance of strengthening safety training, orientation, and practical simulations to enhance students' confidence and awareness of institutional safety mechanisms during tourism-related educational activities.

Table 10

Challenges Respondents Encounter In Implementing Safety Measures during Educational Tours

Indicators	Students	Tour Coordinators	Average Weighted

					Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Sudden weather changes affect travel plans and safety.	3.10	OE	2.90	OE	3.00	OE
2. Managing student behavior during tours can be a challenge as not all students adhere to safety rules.	3.25	OE	3.10	OE	3.17	OE
3. Inadequate preparation or training for staff and students on safety protocols which may lead to confusion during emergencies.	3.00	OE	2.50	SE	3.75	OE
4. Lack of knowledge in unexpected situations may leave student panic in certain situation.	2.95	OE	2.40	SE	2.68	OE
5. The excitement of students during tours sometimes lead to inattentiveness to safety briefing.	2.30	SE	2.80	OE	2.55	OE
6. Limited funding may result in fewer safety resources such as first aid kits, transportation, or security personnel.	2.85	OE	2.40	SE	2.62	OE
7. Too many students could not be handled by tour operators which may result in negligence.	2.81	OE	2.30	SE	2.55	OE
8. Time constraints in packed itineraries sometimes lead to rush safety briefing or incomplete risk assessment.	2.91	OE	2.45	SE	2.68	OE
9. Poorly maintained buses or lack of seat belts can increase risk during travel	2.83	OE	2.40	SE	2.61	OE
10. Lack of practice drills before the trip, leading to confusion in real emergencies.	2.84	OE	2.55	OE	2.70	OE
Average Weighted Mean	2.99	OE	2.58	OE	2.73	OE

The data presented in the table illustrates the challenges encountered by both students and tour coordinators in implementing safety measures during educational tours. The overall weighted average of 2.73, interpreted as “Often Encountered (OE)”, indicates that these challenges occur frequently and have significant implications for the safety and smooth execution of educational trips. The results of the study align closely with Pillar (2023), who emphasized that implementing safety measures during educational tours involves managing large groups of students, supervising behavior, coordinating logistics, and responding to unexpected situations. The top- ranked challenge, “Managing student behavior during tours can be a challenge, as not all students adhere to safety rules” (WM = 3.17, OE), reflects the critical issue of maintaining discipline and adherence to safety protocols, as highlighted by Pillar.

Other frequently encountered challenges, “Sudden weather changes affect travel plans and safety,” “Inadequate preparation or training for staff and students on safety protocols which may lead to confusion during emergencies,” and “Lack of practice drills before the trip leading to confusion in real emergencies”, further support Pillar’s assertion that environmental factors, insufficient training, and inadequate preparedness can increase safety risks during educational excursions.

In comparison, students (Average WM = 2.99) reported encountering these challenges more frequently than

tour coordinators (Average WM = 2.58), which also illustrates Pillar’s point that varying levels of awareness and preparedness among participants can affect the implementation of safety measures, which may reflect students’ limited awareness and preparedness in handling unexpected situations. Overall, the findings indicate that tourism students highly prioritize safety measures that ensure smooth logistics, preparedness for emergencies, and effective communication during tours. Their responses demonstrate an understanding that safety is a shared responsibility between students and organizers and that proactive planning contributes significantly to the overall success and enjoyment of educational tours.

Table 11

Solutions Recommended for Implementing Safety Measures in Educational Tours

Indicators	Students		Tour Coordinators		Average Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Gather feedback from participants and stakeholders for continuous improvement.	3.75	HR	3.80	HR	3.76	HR
2. Distribute safety handbooks with emergency procedures to participants.	3.41	HR	3.85	HR	3.63	HR
3. Provide regular safety drills and training session for both students and staffs to ensure preparedness in emergencies.	3.61	HR	3.85	HR	3.73	HR
4. Always require students to bring their own emergency kits before the educational tour.	3.41	HR	3.90	HR	3.66	HR
5. The school and tour operators should be aware of students’ personal preferences for unusual place.	3.59	HR	4.00	HR	3.80	HR
6. Keep a printed list of all participants with their medical conditions and emergency contacts for quick reference.	3.74	HR	3.85	HR	3.80	HR
7. Check forecasts and assesses risks at the destination before and during the tour to avoid potential hazards.	3.63	HR	3.95	HR	3.79	HR
8. Ensure that vehicles that will be used have been checked before leaving the campus.	3.75	HR	3.95	HR	3.85	HR
9. Have a backup transportation plan in case of unexpected issues or delays.	3.68	HR	4.00	HR	3.84	HR
10. Provide regular safety drills and training sessions for both students and staff to ensure preparedness in emergencies.	3.55	HR	3.85	HR	3.70	HR
Average Weighted Mean	3.61	HR	3.13	R	3.38	HR

The table presents the Solutions Recommended for Implementing Safety Measures during Educational Tours as assessed by tourism students and tour coordinators. Based on the data, the tourism students rated all proposed safety solutions as “*Highly Recommended (HR)*”, with average weighted mean values ranging from 3.63 to 3.85. This

reflects the students' strong agreement on the importance of applying safety protocols to ensure a secure and well-organized educational experience.

Among the proposed solutions, tourism students gave the highest rating to "*Ensure that vehicles that will be used have been checked before leaving the campus*" (WM = 3.75, HR). This shows that students highly value reliable and safe transportation as a crucial part of tour safety. They also emphasized the need to "*Have a backup transportation plan in case of unexpected vehicle issues or delays*" (WM = 3.68, HR), highlighting their awareness of potential travel disruptions and the importance of preparedness.

The lowest-rated recommendation, although still "*Highly Recommended*," is "*Distribute safety handbooks with emergency procedures to participants*" (WM = 3.41, HR). This suggests that while tourism students appreciate written safety guidelines, they may prefer more practical and experiential approaches such as safety drills, orientations, or real-life simulations, over purely informational materials. These results highlight the importance of being prepared, ensuring logistical readiness, and prioritizing medical safety in tour planning, which is also under the DepEd Order 66, s. 2017 or the "*Implementing Guidelines on the Conduct of Off-Campus Activities*". This national order was created to have a well-organized and create a good educational tour experience to all students and people who join the activity.

Overall, the findings indicate that tourism students highly prioritize safety measures that ensure smooth logistics, preparedness for emergencies, and effective communication during tours. Their responses demonstrate an understanding that safety is a shared responsibility between students and organizers and that proactive planning contributes significantly to the overall success and enjoyment of educational tours (**Ferhataj & Memaj, 2024**).

CONCLUSION

It shows that age distribution suggests that the majority of the study's participants are typical college-aged individuals, with a clear distinction between younger students and older coordinators. Such a profile is expected in educational tour settings and ensures the findings are applicable to the target groups involved in tourism excursions.

It shows that respondents' gender indicate that both students and school tour coordinators are predominantly female, highlighting the female-dominated nature of the tourism field in the participating institutions.

It shows that school tour coordinators are highly qualified and possess the necessary educational background to effectively manage and facilitate educational tours. Their advanced education likely contributes to their competence in planning, organizing, and overseeing student excursions.

It shows that the school tour coordinators' extensive experience is a key factor in the efficient organization and smooth execution of educational tours. Their years of service reflect stability and reliability in managing various aspects of tour planning and participant engagement management not only safeguards participants but also enhances the overall quality, learning value, and enjoyment of educational tours.

It shows that perceived risk and safety awareness tour coordinators maintain a commendable level of risk awareness and safety practices during tours, as reflected in the overall *Highly Practiced* rating. Nonetheless, both groups exhibit minor gaps in specific aspects of safety communication and preparedness, particularly in relation to weather readiness and the consistency of safety briefings.

It shows that adherence to safety protocols share a generally strong commitment to safety, as reflected in their high overall ratings. However, a slight difference in perception exists students show moderate preparedness for unforeseen situations, while coordinators demonstrate stronger but slightly inconsistent responsibility for personal emergency belongings. This indicates that while both groups value safety, coordinators exhibit a more practiced adherence, whereas students may need further guidance in proactive safety planning.

It shows confidence in handling emergencies exhibit a high level of confidence in handling emergencies, reflecting their awareness of safety measures and readiness during educational tours. However, the moderately practiced items show that some individuals still rely on external assistance rather than independent action, particularly in managing personal safety tools and responding to minor emergencies. Enhancing personal initiative and readiness will further reinforce their overall emergency response capability.

It shows that perceived effectiveness of school's safety policy is generally perceived as effective in maintaining security and preparedness during educational tours. Both students and coordinators acknowledge the school's strong implementation of safety measures, though time management in transportation remains an area that requires closer attention. This highlights the importance of continuous monitoring and coordination to sustain the high level of safety performance.

It shows that findings indicate students and school tour coordinators differ in their perceptions of safety-related aspects. Tour coordinators, with greater experience and responsibility in managing safety protocols, tend to rate the adequacy and implementation of safety measures higher than students. In contrast, students may have limited exposure and understanding of the school's safety systems, leading to more cautious or less favorable assessments.

It shows that challenges encountered and recommended solutions in implementing safety measures for tourism students' educational tours reveals that student behavior, environmental factors, and preparedness are the primary concerns of participants, reflecting the need for structured planning and vigilance during tours.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Schools shall conduct mandatory safety orientations and training for students and coordinators prior to every educational tour to ensure awareness of safety protocols, emergency procedures, and expected conduct. Regular emergency preparedness programs, including first- aid and safety training, shall also be implemented to strengthen the practical skills and readiness of all participants.

2. Adopt experiential learning methods such as workshops, role-playing, and digital safety simulations to strengthen participants' critical thinking and decision-making skills. These hands-on approaches enhance engagement, improve emergency preparedness, and ensure better application of safety protocols in real tour situations.

3. Educational institutions are encouraged to prioritize the psychological safety and emotional preparedness of students before and during educational tours. Implementing pre-tour counseling sessions or mental health evaluations can assist in identifying and addressing anxiety, fear, or stress that may influence students' engagement or decision-making in critical situations. Integrating psychological support with physical safety protocols ensures a

comprehensive approach to student well-being throughout field-based activities. Including Insurance and Legal Compliance as part of the safety guidelines is essential to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants during tourism students' excursions. Securing travel insurance provides financial and medical assistance in case of accidents, illnesses, or unforeseen emergencies that may occur during the trip. It minimizes potential risks and liabilities for both the students and the institution. Moreover, ensuring compliance with institutional and government policies on educational field trips guarantees that all activities are conducted within legal and safety standards. Adhering to these regulations promotes accountability, safeguards participants' rights, and upholds the credibility and integrity of the academic program.

4. The school should strengthen coordination with transportation providers to ensure punctual arrival and departure of vehicles. Conducting a brief pre-tour logistics meeting among drivers, facilitators, and coordinators can help align schedules, promote time discipline, and reinforce the consistent application of safety standards throughout educational trips.

5. It is recommended that the school formally adopt the Dual-Verification Medical Inventory Protocol as a standard pre-departure procedure. This policy will ensure that emergency medical kits are regularly inspected and verified by both the coordinator and a student representative, promoting accountability, preparedness, and student involvement in maintaining safety standards.

6. Collaborating with local police, medical teams, and disaster response units ensures immediate assistance in case of emergencies and fosters familiarity with local safety procedures. These partnerships can also provide schools with access to expert advice, safety briefings, and on-site support during tours. Strengthening community and institutional collaboration promotes a proactive safety culture and ensures a more secure and well-coordinated learning experience for all participants.

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